

Spatial Empowerment: Combining Participatory and Computational Mapping

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Summary

This paper explores the significance of mapping in understanding a city's geography, emphasizing its role in uncovering place identity and empowering communities. This research combines participatory mapping and computational methods to map neighbourhoods in El Mina's (Tripoli). The methodology employs participatory mapping techniques and volunteered geographical information, juxtaposed with mapping derived from urban elements such as paths, nodes, edges, districts, and landmarks. This study enhances knowledge regarding urban spatial cognition in the Middle East. It is also a rare contribution where quantitative data is mapped in Lebanon outside of Beirut. The data is freely accessible and downloadable to all.

KEYWORDS: cognitive mapping; urban space; place identity; Global South; participatory mapping.

1 Introduction

Mapping is a key part of understanding the geography of the city. It is not only useful to navigate the city but it can also be part of uncovering place identity and building pathways for local empowerment. Understanding and developing spatial definitions, usually operationalised as geographic boundaries, is one of the governing instruments required for city making. These definitions help identify and organise different areas within a city, which is crucial for effective urban planning and development. Additionally, they provide a common language for policymakers, planners, and residents to discuss and address the specific needs and challenges of different parts of the city. In certain Global South countries, these spatial boundaries are currently delineated only for broader geographical scales, such as regions and districts, but have not been officially established for local neighbourhoods. This is the case in Lebanon. This paper contributes to filling some 'gaps on the map' by combining participatory mapping and computational approaches to the perception of the

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city (Lynch, 1960), specifically focusing on El Mina’s (Tripoli) neighbourhoods (Chambers, 2006; Gressel et al., 2020).

The concept of spatial empowerment through participatory mapping revolves around the idea of democratising spatial planning and decision-making processes in urban areas. By involving local citizens in the creation of maps that reflect their lived experiences, needs, and aspirations, a more inclusive and holistic representation of the urban landscape emerges. This sense of ownership and agency empowers communities, as they become active contributors to the development and planning of their neighbourhoods (Brown et al., 2017). Concurrently, computational approaches to mental imagery and people’s perception of the city (Filomena et al., 2019) offer an alternative form of spatial empowerment by capitalising on open source data and network science techniques to identify neighbourhoods derived from key urban elements such as paths, nodes, edges, districts, and landmarks (Lynch, 1960).

Traditional zoning practices often rely on top-down approaches that may overlook the nuanced realities of local communities. As argued by Brown et al. (2018) public participation in the development of general land use plans has rarely used participatory mapping methods that engage the general public to explicitly inform zoning decisions. Only in recent years has participatory mapping experienced significant growth in applications (Brown and Kytta, 2014; Mukherjee, 2015). Participatory mapping results in locally generated data that can serve as a powerful resource for urban planners, policymakers, and researchers, thus offering a more accurate and comprehensive understanding of the urban fabric.

This study enhances knowledge regarding urban spatial cognition in the Middle East, an area that has received limited attention thus far, by creating operational neighbourhood for El Mina. As quantitative data is mapped in Lebanon outside of Beirut very rarely, this work also contributes to spatial empowerment of left-behind places (Fawaz et al., 2018; Price-Chalita, 1994). This data is being prepared to be freely accessible and downloadable to all and will aid in the improvement of GIS data sources in areas with limited data.

2 Context

El Mina is a Mediterranean coastal city located in the North Governorate of Lebanon. It is adjacent to Tripoli and considered as its harbour. Historically, El Mina was known as ‘Al Iskila’ meaning ‘the harbour’ and was Tripoli’s port area. El Mina is approximately 80 km from Beirut and covers an area of 3.737 Km² divided in four main cadastres, Mina 1, Mina 2, Mina 3 and Mina Jardins as shown in Figure 1. The municipality describes different quarters within the city, denominating them as ancient quarters; transitional quarters; new quarters; and modern and public neighbourhoods (Municipality of El Mina, 2020). Each of these quarters contain different neighbourhoods that do not have any formal official boundaries and were named following historical anecdotes.

Figure 1: Tripoli in context

3 Participatory Mapping

Five main sources were used in order to define El Mina’s neighbourhoods; of which two secondary sources were used as a starting point: UN-Habitat’s neighbourhood mapping in the Tripoli City Profile (2016, p. 102) and El Mina Municipality’s list of neighbourhoods available on the municipality’s website (2020). Starting from these secondary sources, we employed participatory mapping techniques and Volunteered Geographical Information (VGI) to delineate neighbourhoods. Our approach was characterised by methodological pluralism, with two common methods being qualitative mapping using stakeholder and resident interviews and quantitative methods that engage larger public samples (Brown et al., 2017).

The qualitative consultation drew upon four primary sources, including a stakeholders’ consultation workshop with former and current municipal members; a mukhtar (local administrator), and representatives of local and international NGOs working in the city; street interviews with 16 residents; a consultation workshop with the 18 citizen scientists, and follow-up consultations with citizen scientists which had conducted the street interviews. The consultations were adopted to triangulate the neighbourhoods’ boundaries as well as the characteristics of the city’s diverse areas. Although our sampling stratification was limited, given the qualitative nature of the consultations, we actively involved stakeholders and residents from diverse socio-economic and national backgrounds. The process became a platform for amplifying voices that might otherwise be marginalised or overlooked. This inclusiveness not only contributed to a more comprehensive and accurate representation of areas and spaces within the city but also enhanced the legitimacy of the mapping outcomes.

Following all the consultations, nine maps were produced (see Figure 2). These maps serve as a translation of the drawings collaboratively generated by the engaged participants.

The final image of the neighbourhoods as defined by the participatory mapping is shown in Figure 3.

4 Computational Neighbourhoods

Lynch has described neighbourhoods (*districts*) as ‘city areas which the observer can mentally go inside of, and which have some common character’ (p. 66 Lynch, 1960) Citizens and visitors identify and distinguish them thanks to a set of ‘thematic continuities’ perceived across the urban space. Following these ideas, within the Space Syntax community, scholars have argued that the topology of the street network can be analysed to identify districts in a way that would align with people’s perceptions, rather than administrative definitions (Turner, 2007; Law, 2017). Here, the modularity optimisation algorithm, a technique for community detection in networks, is performed to identify sub-graphs (representing separate neighbourhoods) from the street topology (for details, see: Filomena et al., 2019) of El-Mina.

5 Final Mapping

By systematically carrying out these two processes and seamlessly integrating the outcomes of both mapping exercises, we culminate in the creation of the final comprehensive map. Our final repre-

sensation of the city geographies is presented in Figure 4. Here, the integration of participatory mapping and computational methods has yielded a comprehensive and dynamic approach to mapping neighbourhoods in El Mina, Tripoli. By actively involving the community in the mapping process, a wealth of local knowledge and insights has been incorporated, enriching the spatial representation of the neighbourhood. The synergy of traditional participatory methods with cutting-edge computational techniques has not only provided a detailed and accurate depiction of the area but has also fostered community engagement and empowerment. This holistic mapping approach stands out as a model for future urban research endeavours, emphasising the importance of collaboration between residents and technological advancements in creating more inclusive and responsive urban landscapes. By embracing an open-source approach, the information becomes a shared resource for urban planners, researchers, and community members alike. This not only enhances transparency but also promotes the democratisation of data, fostering collaborative efforts towards sustainable urban development.

6 References and Citations

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8 Biography

Elisabetta Pietrostefani is a Lecturer in Geographic Data Science at the University of Liverpool interested in applying data and technologies to improve the understanding of urban development and inequalities. She holds a PhD in Planning Policy and Urban Economics from the London School of Economics.

Gabriele Filomena looks into the relationship between cognition and cities. Alongside network analysis and agent-based modelling, he enjoys working with qualitative methods and using cartographic visualisation to represent human-related data. Before joining the University of Liverpool as a Lecturer in Geographic Data Science, he obtained a PhD in Geoinformatics at the University of Muenster.

Figure 3: Computational Neighbourhoods

Figure 4: El Mina proposed neighbourhood mapping